

Oxidation of Thiourea by *N*-Bromosuccinimide. A Kinetic Study

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The kinetic of oxidation of thiourea with *N*-bromosuccinimide (NBS) has been studied. The oxidation reaction is kinetically of the second order, being first order with respect to both thiourea and NBS. The rate increases with increase of pH and decrease of dielectric constant of the medium. The addition of NaCl and NaNO₃ electrolytes to the reaction mixture shows negative salt effect.

THIOUREA has several industrial, medicinal and analytical applications. Kinetics of oxidation of thiourea with various oxidants have been reported in the literature. The nature of oxidation product depends upon nature of oxidant and experimental conditions¹. The study of literature reveals that a detailed kinetic study of the reaction between thiourea and NBS and particularly the effect of dielectric constant of solvent and concentration of electrolyte upon rate is lacking. In the present article therefore, an attempt has been made to study the effect of solvent, pH and electrolyte on the rate of the reaction between thiourea and NBS.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were either of AnalaR or G.R. (E. Merck) grade. Reactant solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. Kinetics were followed by estimating residual thiourea or *N*-bromosuccinimide iodometrically at different intervals of time.

N-Bromosuccinimide and thiourea were crystallised before use. To avoid photochemical effects, reaction bottles blackened from outside were used and suspended in a water-thermostat for at least 30 min before starting the reaction. Kinetic measurements were reproducible within 2.0% error. Kinetics of the reaction between thiourea and NBS was studied in aqueous and aquo-organic solvent mixtures, in buffer solutions having pH range from 2.0 to 4.0, and by adding different amounts of various electrolytes at constant temperature.

Results and Discussion

Effect of varying the concentration: The pseudo-first order rate constant (k_1) increases on increasing the concentration of the substrate (thiourea) or (oxidant) and keeping the concentration of oxidant (NBS) or (substrate) fixed (Table 1).

The plots of $\log k_1$ vs $\log [S]$ and the double reciprocal plot, $1/k_1$ vs $1/[S]$ are linear at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The ratio of first order rate constant to the corresponding substrate concentration, i.e. $k_1/[S]$ or $k_1/[OX]$ is constant (Table 1). The overall order for the oxidation of thiourea with NBS is, thus, two. The reaction is also of second order with rate constant values of 6.40×10^{-3} and 8.95×10^{-3} dm³ mol⁻¹ min⁻¹ at 30 and 35°, respectively.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION OF REACTIONS ON THE RATE OF OXIDATION AT $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$

Sl. no.	Concn. of substrate (Thiourea) $\times 10^3$ M	Concentration of oxidant (NBS) $\times 10^3$ M	$K_1 \times 10^3$ min ⁻¹	$k_1/[S]$ or $k_1/[OX]$
1.	1.60	8.00	5.45	0.34
2.	2.00	8.00	7.14	0.36
3.	2.40	8.00	8.82	0.37
4.	2.80	8.00	9.84	0.35
5.	0.05	5.00	20.00	4.00
6.	0.05	6.00	23.20	3.86
7.	0.05	7.00	26.00	3.71
8.	0.05	9.00	31.50	3.50

Effect of solvent: The rate of oxidation of thiourea with NBS has been studied in water and its mixture with methanol and isopropanol, dimethyl formamide (DMF) and dioxane, and results are presented in Table 2. The plot of $\log k_1$ vs $1/D$ is linear. The increase in the content of organic co-solvent results in a decrease of dielectric constant of the medium and an increase of the reaction rate. This may indicate that in presence of organic co-solvent, solvation of the activated complex leading to the formation of intermediate is facilitated. Similar behaviour has been observed for the reaction between thiourea and copper sulphate in water-dioxane solvents².

TABLE 2—VALUES OF RATE CONSTANT (k_2) AND DIELECTRIC CONSTANTS FOR OXIDATION OF THIOUREA WITH NBS IN ORGANIC—WATER SOLVENT MIXTURES

Solvent wt. %	Methanol—Water at 25°		Ethanol—Water at 30°		Isopropanol—Water at 30°		DMF—Water at 30°		Dioxane—Water at 35°	
	D	$k_2 \times 10^3$	D	$k_2 \times 10^3$	D	$k_2 \times 10^3$	D	$k_2 \times 10^3$	D	$k_2 \times 10^3$
0							76.55	6.40	74.83	8.95
5									71.22	20.00
10	74.10	7.79	71.23	9.00	69.72	9.00	72.48	16.00	67.60	30.00
20	69.21	9.30	65.3	15.60	62.64	16.00	68.41	33.00		
30	64.36	11.90	59.68	21.10	55.55	23.00	64.34	40.00		
40	59.65	13.40	53.78	28.60	48.46	39.80	60.27	116.50		
50	55.00	17.90	47.84	41.80	41.42	45.00	56.21	309.00		
60	50.55	29.80	42.34	51.10	34.36	55.00				

Effect of pH: The kinetics of the reaction was studied in the pH range 2.0–4.0 by using standard buffer solutions at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. It has been found from the values of rate constants (Table 3) that the rate of reaction increases gradually with the increase of pH in the range 2.40–3.60. At pH 2.0, the rate is too slow and at pH 4.0 it is too fast to be measured accurately. Apparently, the pH range 2.40–3.60 is most suitable to study the effect.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF pH ON SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANT AT $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$

Sl. no.	pH	Buffer solution added	$[H^+] \times 10^4$	$k_2 \times 10^3$
1.	2.40	HCl/KHC ₈ H ₄ O ₄	39.80	1.40
2.	2.80	HCl/KHO ₈ H ₄ O ₄	15.85	3.33
3.	3.00	HCl/KHC ₈ H ₄ O ₄	10.00	5.45
4.	3.20	HCl/KHC ₈ H ₄ O ₄	6.31	7.50
5.	3.60	HCl/KHC ₈ H ₄ O ₄	2.51	16.40
6.	4.00	NaOH/KHC ₈ H ₄ O ₄	1.00	125.00

A plot of $\log k_2$ vs $\log[H^+]$ is linear with a slope of approximately one. This indicates that one hydrogen ion is participating in the rate determining step. Similar behaviour has been observed by Mohan and Rao³ in the acid-catalysed hydrolysis of 2,4-dihydroxyacetophenoneisonicotinoylhydrazine. The plot of $1/k_2$ vs $[H^+]$ is also linear (Fig. 1).

Effect of electrolytes: In a series of experiments, the effect of NaCl and NaNO₃ electrolytes on the reaction rate has been studied at $35.0 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and data are given in Table 4. It is found from the values of rate constant (k_2) that the rate of reaction decreases with an increase in ionic strength of sodium chloride or sodium nitrate, indicating negative salt-effect.

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF ELECTROLYTES ON SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANT AT $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$

Electrolyte	Concn. of electrolyte in reaction mixture g dm ⁻³	$k_2 \times 10^3$
NaCl	5.85	8.00
	11.70	7.40
	23.40	6.40
	35.10	5.45
NaNO ₃	8.49	7.14
	16.98	6.66
	33.96	5.83
	50.94	5.00

Fig. 1. Plot of $1/k_2$ vs $[H^+]$.

The plot of $\log k_2$ vs ionic strength (μ) and k_2 vs concentration of different electrolytes are linear having definite intercept on the rate axis satisfying the requirement of respective equations (1) and (2)⁴,

$$\ln k = k_0 + (b_0 + b_A - b_+)$$
 (1)

or

$$k = k_0 + b | \text{salt} |$$
 (2)

Thermodynamic parameters: For the present study using linear least-square method, the thermodynamic parameters values calculated at 30° are

$$E_a, 6.23 (\pm 0.4) \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}; \Delta H^\ddagger, 5.6 (\pm 0.5) \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}; A, 1.84 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}; \text{ and } \Delta S^\ddagger, -61.75 (\pm 1.34) \text{ e.u.}$$

Mechanism: In the present study, it has been shown that thiourea is oxidised to formamidine disulphide with a single electron transfer as

The mechanism of the reaction of thiourea with NBS is given as

From the proposed mechanism, the rate of reaction can be given as

$$\frac{d[\text{product}]}{dt} = k [\text{NBS}] [\text{Th}]$$

The effect of $[\text{H}^+]$ on rate of reaction can be explained as follows. In the acidic medium, the NBS is protonated. Since the reaction of NBS with thiourea involves homolytic cleavage of NBS, any factor facilitating such cleavage would result

in the increase of rate of such reaction and any factor which deaccelerates the homolytic cleavage of NBS would result in the decrease of rate of reaction. The homolytic cleavage of NBS and NBSH^+ can be presented as below,

The species (II) and (III) are clearly less stable than (I) and therefore, their formation from NBSH^+ would be slower than the formation of (I) from NBS; hence, the rate of reaction will be lower with protonated NBS. In other words, the increase in hydrogen ion concentration would decrease the rate of reaction as has been experimentally observed.

Product identification: The above mechanism is supported by the formation and identification of the products of the oxidation. Formamidine disulphide, as one of the products from the oxidation of thiourea with NBS has been identified by formation of its dihydrochloride⁵ and sulphate salts. The sulphate (m.p. 148°) and dihydrochloride (m.p. 166°) salts of the end-product formamidine disulphide were prepared by the method of Priesler and Berger⁶.

The compounds were characterised by their elemental analysis, melting points, infrared spectral data and their qualitative reduction to thiourea with zinc and acid as reported by Verma and Kumar⁷. Melting point and ir spectra of the dihydrochloride salt are the same as reported by Hoffmann and Edwards⁸. Formation of formamidine disulphide as one of the oxidation products has also been reported by oxidation of thiourea with potassium bromide, 2,2-dichlorophenol-indophenol and copper sulphate.

In short, the reaction between thiourea and NBS is of second order and the rate depends on the dielectric constant of the medium, pH and the ionic strength of the salts present in the reaction system.

References

1. B. SINGH and B C. VERMA, *J. Sci Ind Res.*, 1965, 24, 536.
2. M H JAGDALE and S N. KHODASKAR, *J. Shivaji Univ. (Sci)*, 1976, 16, 41
3. M. M MOHAN and S B. RAO, *J. Indian Chem Soc.*, 1981, 58, 571.
4. A A. FROST and R. G PEARSON, *Kinetics and Mechanism*, Wiley Eastern, New Delhi, 1970, p 152
5. M. HAFEMANN and J. O EDWARDS, *Inorg Chem*, 1977, 16, 3333.
6. P. W PRIESTER and L BERGER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc*, 1947, 69, 322.
7. B. C. VERMA and S. KUMAR, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1974, 29, 1240.